

References

1. G. N. SARKAR and J. L. DAS KANUNGO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 358.
2. J. L. DAS KANUNGO and S. K. CHAKRAVARTI, *Kolloid Z. and Z. Polym.*, 1972, **250**, 891.
3. C. KRISHNAMOORTHY and R. OVERSTREET, *Soil Sci.*, 1950, **69**, 41.
4. R. H. STOKES and R. A. ROBINSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1870.
5. J. L. PAULRY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 1422.
6. R. M. BARRER, W. BUSER and W. F. GRUTTER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1956, **39**, 518.
7. R. M. BARRER and W. M. MEIER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, **54**, 1074.
8. R. M. BARRER and W. M. MEIER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1959, **55**, 130.
9. F. HEFFERICH, "Ion Exchange", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962, p. 186.
10. P. G. SLADE, M. RAUPACH and W. W. EMERSON, *Clays and Clay Miner.*, 1978, **26**, 125.
11. B. K. G. THENG, *New Zealand J. Sci.*, 1971, **14**, 1026.
12. E. F. VANSANT and L. VANHOOF, *J. Royal Netherlands Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **97**, 191.
13. J. J. FRIPIAT, A. SERVAIS and A. LEONARD, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1962, **3**, 617.

Densities and Excess Volumes for Four Binary Mixtures of Ethyl Acetate with Toluene, Ethyl Benzene, Carbon Tetrachloride and Chloroform at 303.15 K

S. L. OSWAL* and M. V. RATHNAM

Department of Chemistry, South Gujarat University,
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IN continuation of our earlier studies^{1,2} on molecular interactions between components of binary mixtures of esters with polar and non-polar solvents, we report the densities and excess volumes for four binary solution of ethyl acetate+toluene, ethyl acetate+ethyl benzene, ethyl acetate+carbon tetrachloride and ethyl acetate+chloroform at 303.15 K.

Experimental

Ethyl acetate (B.D.H. AnalaR), ethyl benzene (Fluka AG), toluene (AnalaR), carbon tetrachloride B.D.H. (spectroscopic), chloroform (B.D.H. spectroscopic) were further purified by standard procedures given by Riddick and Bunger³. All these chemicals were fractionally distilled just before use. Ethyl benzene (Fluka AG) of purity > 99% was used as received. The purity of the purified liquids were checked by measuring refractive indices at 303.15 K which agreed well with the literature values^{3,4}. The densities were measured with the help of a pycnometer having a bulb volume 11 cm³ approximately, calibrated against water and benzene. The apparatus used and the procedure followed are described elsewhere⁵. The density data are correct to ± 0.0001 units. The temperature of the water thermostat was

TABLE 1—DENSITIES (d) AND EXCESS VOLUMES (V^E) FOR ETHYL ACETATE+TOLUENE, + ETHYL BENZENE, + CARBON TETRACHLORIDE, + CHLOROFORM AT 303.15 K. X_1 IS THE MOLE FRACTION OF ETHYL ACETATE

X_1	d (g cm ⁻³)	V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)
(i) Ethyl acetate + toluene		
0.0	0.8577	—
0.0539	0.8592	+0.011
0.1609	0.8624	-0.003
0.3177	0.8673	-0.030
0.4188	0.8703	-0.025
0.5183	0.8736	-0.035
0.5723	0.8752	-0.040
0.6215	0.8766	-0.029
0.8586	0.8842	-0.025
0.9543	0.8872	-0.008
1.0	0.8885	—
(ii) Ethyl acetate + ethyl benzene		
0.0	0.8583	—
0.0533	0.8596	0.009
0.0979	0.8606	0.019
0.1926	0.8629	0.041
0.3714	0.8677	0.047
0.4541	0.8701	0.056
0.5748	0.8734	0.067
0.6533	0.8759	0.071
0.7279	0.8785	0.051
0.7991	0.8808	0.062
0.8661	0.8832	0.043
0.9336	0.8858	0.028
1.0	0.8885	—
(iii) Ethyl acetate + carbon tetrachloride		
0.0	1.5748	—
0.0667	1.5281	0.018
0.1673	1.4582	0.022
0.2628	1.3920	0.030
0.3959	1.3001	0.041
0.5679	1.1820	0.043
0.6611	1.1179	0.047
0.7657	1.0468	0.027
0.8641	0.9804	0.016
0.9263	0.9383	0.013
1.0	0.8885	—
(iv) Ethyl acetate + chloroform		
0.0	1.4706	—
0.0548	1.4328	-0.043
0.1407	1.3745	-0.058
0.2285	1.3170	-0.068
0.3553	1.2370	-0.049
0.4476	1.1813	-0.023
0.5145	1.1423	-0.007
0.5486	1.1226	+0.010
0.6163	1.0847	+0.024
0.6550	1.0694	+0.036
0.7302	1.0233	+0.026
0.7658	1.0047	+0.023
0.8425	0.9655	+0.022
1.0	0.8885	—

maintained at 303.15 \pm 0.02 K. The densities of purified liquids were in close agreement with the literature data^{3,4}. Mixtures were prepared by weighing the liquids in ground stoppered weighing flasks on a Metler (MERA-WAG-GDANSK, Poland) balance, accurate to 10⁻⁵ g.

* Author for correspondence.

Fig. 1. Molar excess volume V^E $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ for ethyl acetate + toluene \circ ; + ethyl benzene Δ ; + carbon tetrachloride \bullet ; and + chloroform \blacktriangle ; at 303.15 K. X_1 is the mole fraction of ethyl acetate.

Results and Discussion

Densities were measured at 303.15 K over the entire range of composition for all the four systems. The excess volumes V^E were calculated from these density data using the relation (1)

$$V^E = (M_1 X_1 + M_2 X_2) / d_{12} - (M_1 X_1 / d_1 + M_2 X_2 / d_2) \dots (1)$$

where M , X and d represent molecular weight, mole fraction and density, respectively. Subscripts 1, 2 and 12 refer to pure components and mixtures respectively. The data of densities and excess volumes are given in Table 1.

The excess volumes for mixtures ethyl acetate + ethyl benzene and ethyl acetate + carbon tetrachloride are small but positive. For ethyl acetate + toluene they are negative but changes sign when the mixture has greater than 0.85 mole fraction of toluene. For ethyl acetate + chloroform the excess volumes have S-shaped curve with maximum and minimum at 0.665 and 0.228 mole fraction of ethyl acetate respectively (Fig. 1).

It is informative to compare the present results of the mixtures ethyl acetate + toluene, ethyl acetate + ethyl benzene, ethyl acetate + carbon tetrachloride and ethyl acetate + chloroform with the results for cyclohexane + ethyl acetate and benzene + ethyl acetate². Values of excess volumes of equimolar mixture of ethyl acetate + cyclohexane, + benzene, + toluene, + ethyl benzene, + carbon tetrachloride, + chloroform are 1.2, 0.12, -0.042, 0.066, 0.039 and -0.002 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$, respectively. We observed that for cyclohexane + ethyl acetate excess volumes are highly positive but its magnitude reduces markedly

by changing cyclohexane to benzene, toluene, ethyl benzene, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform. It is easy to explain the expansion in case of ethyl acetate + cyclohexane system which may be due to breaking of bonds amongst the ethyl acetate clusters by the addition of cyclohexane. This marked reduction in excess volume in case of benzene, toluene, ethyl benzene, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform systems suggests that breaking of bonds in ethyl acetate as well as formation of complex between the two unlike components may be taking place due to the specific interaction between them.

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References

1. S. L. OSWAL and K. G. PATHAK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1982, 21A, 712.
2. S. L. OSWAL and K. G. PATHAK, *Vidya B., J. Gujarat University*, (Communicated).
3. J. A. RIDDICK and W. B. BUNGER, "Organic Solvents-Physical Properties and Methods of Purification", 3rd Edn., Wiley Interscience, N. Y., 1970.
4. J. TIMMERMANS, "Physico-Chemical Constants of Pure Organic Compounds", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1950, Vol 1; 1965, Vol 2.
5. S. L. OSWAL, *Indian J. Chem. Educ.*, 1980, 7, 12.